

PRODUCT AND ITS FEATURES

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Abstract

Product is one of the important elements of marketing mix. A marketer can satisfy the needs and wants of consumers through the product. A product is both a good and a service. Decisions about all other elements of the marketing mix depend on the product. For example, a price is set for a product; advertising efforts are aimed at selling the product; and a distribution network is prepared for the product. The product is at the heart of the marketing program. Therefore, the product plays a major role in determining the overall success of the marketing efforts. This article describes the product and its features.

Keywords. Product, product characteristics, sales goods, price, sales success, marketing.

Аннотация

Продукт является одним из важных элементов комплекса маркетинга. Маркетолог может удовлетворить потребности и желания потребителей с помощью продукта. Товар – это и товар, и услуга. Решения относительно всех других элементов комплекса маркетинга зависят от продукта. Например, на товар устанавливается цена; рекламные усилия направлены на продажу товара; и для продукта подготовлена дистрибьюторская сеть. Продукт находится в центре маркетинговой программы. Таким образом, продукт играет важную роль в определении общего успеха маркетинговых усилий. В этой статье описывается продукт и его функции.

Ключевые слова. Продукт, характеристики продукта, товары для продажи, цена, успех продаж, маркетинг.

INTRODUCTION

Product is a bundle of benefits-physical and psychological- that marketer wants to offer, or a bundle of expectations that consumers want to fulfill. Marketer can satisfy needs and wants of target consumers by products. Product includes both good and service. Normally, product is taken as a tangible object, such as a pen, television set, bread, book, vehicle, table, etc. But, tangible product is a package of services or benefits.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Marketer should consider product benefits and services, instead of product itself. Importance lies in the services rendered by the product, and not tangible object itself. People are not interested just possessing products, but the services rendered by the products.

They include after-sales services, installation, guarantee and warranty, free home delivery, free repairing, and so forth. As per the definition, anything which can satisfy need and want of consumers is a product. Thus, product may be in form of physical object, person, idea, activity, or organisation that can provide any kind of services that satisfy some customer needs or wants

Careful analysis of concept of product essentially reveals following features:

1. Product is one of the elements of marketing mix or programme.
2. Different people perceive it differently. Management, society, and consumers have different expectations.
3. Product includes both good and service.
4. Marketer can actualize its goals by producing, selling, improving, and modifying the product.
5. Product is a base for entire marketing programme.
6. In marketing terminology, product means a complete product that can be sold to consumers. That means branding, labeling, colour, services, etc., constitute the product.
7. Product includes total offers, including main qualities, features, and services.
8. It includes tangible and non-tangible features or benefits.
9. It is a vehicle or medium to offer benefits and satisfaction to consumers.
10. Important lies in services rendered by the product, and not ownership of product. People buy services, and not the physical object.

Such products improve or enhance users' convenience. They are used in a day-to-day life. They are frequently required and can be easily purchased. For example, soaps, biscuits, toothpaste, razors and shaving creams, newspapers, etc. They are purchased spontaneously, without much consideration, from nearby shops or retail malls.

These products require special time and shopping efforts. They are purchased purposefully from special shops or markets. Quality, price, brand, fashion, style, getup, colour, etc., are important criteria to be considered. They are to be chosen among various alternatives or varieties. Gold and jewellerys, footwear, clothes, and other durables (including refrigerator, television, wrist washes, etc.).

RESULTS

Durable products can last for a longer period and can be repeatedly used by one or more persons. Television, computer, refrigerator, fans, electric irons, vehicles, etc., are examples of durable products. Brand, company image, price, qualities (including safety, ease, economy, convenience, durability, etc.), features (including size, colour, shape, weight, etc.), and after-sales services (including free installation, home delivery, repairing, guarantee and warranty, etc.) are important aspects the customers consider while buying these products.

As against durable products, the non-durable products have short life. They must be consumed within short time after they are manufactured. Fruits, vegetables, flowers, cheese, milk, and other provisions are non-durable in nature. They are used for once. They are also known as consumables. Mostly, many of them are non-branded. They are frequently purchased products and can be easily bought from nearby outlets. Freshness, packing, purity, and price are important criteria to purchase these products.

CONCLUSION

Industrial products are used as the inputs by manufacturing firms for further processes on the products, or manufacturing other products. Some products are both industrial as well as consumer products. Machinery, components, certain chemicals, supplies and services, etc., are some industrial products.

Again, strict classification in term of industrial consumer and consumer products is also not possible, for example, electricity, petroleum products, sugar, cloth, wheat, computer, vehicles, etc., are used by industry as the inputs while the same products are used by consumers for their daily use as well.

Some companies, for example, electricity, cements, petrol and coals, etc., sell their products to industrial units as well as to consumers. As against consumer products, the marketing of industrial products differs in many ways.

References:

1. E.E. Amanov. Islohotlarni chuqurlashtirish jarayonida iqtisodiy o'sish va uning omillari. Iqtisod fanlari nomzodi ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan dissertatsiya. T., 2005.
2. A. M. Babushkina. Gosudarstvennoe regulirovanie natsionalnoy ekonomiki. Uchebnoe posobie. M.: Finansi i statistika. 2004.
3. E.F. Borisov. Ekonomicheskaya teoriya: ucheb. 2-e izd., pererab. i dop. - M.: TK Velbi, Izd-vo «Prospekt», 2005.
4. Brendelyova E.A. Neoinstitutsionalnaya teoriya. Ucheb. posob. - M.: TEIS, 2003.
5. V poiskax novoy teorii s problemnimi situatsiyami. Ucheb. posob. / Pod red. A.G. Gryaznovoy. i dr. - M.: KNO RUS, 2004.

6. Vexi ekonomicheskoy misli. Ekonomicheskoe blagosostoyanie i obshchestvennyy vikor, tom 4. - SPb. 2004.

